

Speculation on Quantum Interaction Related Information Paired with Uncertainty Part 2

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 2, 2024

In Part I, we argued that spin $\frac{1}{2}$ arises from a localization constraint applied to a rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$ at t in special relativity. We argued that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, parts of the free particle quantum wavefunction, follow from the degeneracy of the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et+px$ for $x=x_0+n\hbar/p$ and $t=t_0+n\hbar/E$ ($n=\text{integer}$) converted into the form of a probability. This follows from the constraint $v=x'/t'$ imposed on the particle as seen by a frame moving with constant $-v$. We argued that the localisation constraint m_0 at $x=0$ ($y=0, z=0$) should also have quantum mechanical consequences and argued that it might be linked to spin $\frac{1}{2}$.

Here we consider the procedure of Dirac in linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation. This equation follows as an inner product from special relativity with $E \rightarrow i\partial/\partial t$ and $p = -i\text{grad}$. The two 4-vectors in question are: (pc, E) and $(0, m_0 c^2)$. In linear algebra, even if the inner product of two vectors is the same, that does not mean the vectors themselves are the same. In other words, one does not have an equality at the vector level. The linearization of the Klein-Gordon equation is in a sense trying to isolate the individual vectors, but not in vector form, otherwise one cannot obtain an equation. This suggests that there is something connecting $(0, m_0 c^2)$ and (pc, E) beyond the Lorentz transformation, we argue. In particular, we suggest that creating an equation means using matrices (as Dirac already showed) and these are operators. In particular, even though these operators do not act directly on any space-time variables, they are connected with space-time because they have indices linked with x, y, z, t i.e. multiply with E, p_x, p_y, p_z . Furthermore, they do not commute. These two points, we argue, suggest that one does not have spherical symmetry or isotropy in space, but rather, like angular momentum's $Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$, one has localization, namely that of m_0 at $x=0$ because the matrices do not really disappear even if $p_x=p_y=p_z=0$.

In other words, we try to argue the assertion that localization of m_0 at rest at $x=0$ leads to spin $\frac{1}{2}$ in a more quantitative way than the suggestion given in Part I.

Quantum Mechanics and Constraints

We argued in detail in Part I, that free particle $\exp(ipx) \exp(-iEt)$ quantum mechanics arises from the degeneracy of $A = -Et+px$ (Lorentz invariant). This Lorentz invariant, in turn, arises from the constraint $x'/t'=v$ which applies to a rest mass at $x=0$, t being viewed from a frame moving with constant $-v$.

We then suggested in Part I, that the localization of m_0 at $x=0$ ($y=0, z=0$) at rest, is a constraint and should lead to quantum mechanical consequences and suggested that in fact this leads to spin. Here we try to quantify this idea.

Dirac Approach to Spin $\frac{1}{2}$

Dirac linearized the Klein-Gordon equation:

$$- \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} \text{partial} W(x,t) = - \text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} W + m_0 m_0 W \quad ((1))$$

to an equation containing $\partial/\partial t$, $-\text{grad}$ and m_0 as well as 4×4 matrices and 4-vectors (two sets of spinors). He noted that one is forced to use matrices in order to obtain an equation which when multiplied by itself yields the Klein-Gordon equation. This leads to anticommuting matrices.

We note that the Klein-Gordon follows from an inner product in special relativity:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2 \quad (c=1) \quad ((2))$$

From linear algebra, it is known that various vectors may have the same modulus, but are different entities. In other words, there is no equation equating the two as the Dirac equation does for:

$$(pc, E) \quad \text{and} \quad (0, m_0 c c) \quad ((3))$$

This begs the question: Why not leave the two vectors ((3)) as they are and not linearize the Klein-Gordon equation? We suggest that Dirac's approach is linked with an idea that goes beyond the Lorentz transformation, namely the nature of constraints in the problem. In other words, $(0, m_0 c c)$ is a state which is constrained or localized at $x=0, t$ to which one introduces a second constraint (view from a frame moving at $-v$ with $x'/t'=v$) to obtain p and E . We thus suggest that there should be consequences to the constraint of the localized m_0 which carries over to the (pc, E) state which exhibits further constraints. Given that $\exp(-i m_0 c c t)$ holds in the rest frame, the effects of the localized mass should also hold in the moving frame (i.e. spin holds for both an m_0 at rest and one that is moving.)

For example, we have argued that $A = -Et + px$ gives rise to $\exp(ipx)\exp(-iEt)$ due to the degeneracy of A . In the rest frame, one has:

$$\exp(-i m_0 c c t) \quad A = -m_0 c c t \quad ((4))$$

Thus, there is degeneracy in A for $t=t_0 + n \cdot \hbar / m_0 c c$. ((5))

We suggest that the localisation leads to further consequence and suggest that one may in fact seek an equation linking (pc, E) and $(0, m_0 c c)$ which are vectors which would not normally be linked by an equation (at the vector level, only at the modulus level).

To create such an equation requires 4×4 matrices as Dirac has shown. These four matrices are labeled by x, y, z, t (or associated with p_x, p_y, p_z, E) implying they are somehow linked to space-time even though they do not explicitly act directly on any spacetime variable like $\partial/\partial t$ or $-\text{grad}$.

Dirac showed that his matrices anticommute and had the further property (1) that they anticommute. This means that they do not commute, or that acting with Matrix (x) Matrix (y) is not the same as acting with Matrix (y) Matrix (x) .

We suggest that this result means that one does not have isotropy in space and assign this to the localization of m_0 at $x=0$. This non-commuting result is very similar to that found for the angular momentum operators, but in that case, there are specific spatial variables, namely θ and ϕ . In other words, by trying to force an equation linking the vectors (pc, E) and $(0, m_0 c c)$

(which would not be done in linear algebra), one introduces matrices which imply non-isotropy of space.

The matrices form a dot product with E, p_x, p_y, p_z in Dirac's formalism, but even if $p_x=0, p_y=0, p_z=0$, we suggest that these matrices do not disappear. In other words, they should apply to a particle at rest, i.e. it too has spin $\frac{1}{2}$.

Case of a Photon

We note that a photon has spin 1 and does not have a rest frame. Thus, localization constraints which apply to m_0 at $x=0, (y=0, z=0)$ at rest (spin $\frac{1}{2}$) do not apply to a photon. In fact, it has no constraints of localization, but it does have 3-axis even though the momentum vector lies in one direction. Thus, for circularly polarized light, one may have actual physical angular momentum linked with a photon.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argued in Part I, that spin $1/2$ might arise from localization constraints on a rest mass, m_0 , at $x=0$ at t . In this note, we try to quantify this by first noting that the Klein-Gordon equation follows from the special relativistic inner product $E^2 - p^2 = m_0^2 c^4$ ($c=1$). An inner product links vectors which have the same modulus, but are otherwise not equal. In such a case, one would not create an equation linking (pc, E) and $(0, m_0 c c)$ in linear form, unless there is a deeper reason for doing so. We suggest that free particle quantum mechanics arises from special relativity, but is linked to constraints. We suggest that $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$, but also $\exp(-i m_0 c c t)$ in the rest frame, follow from $A = -Et + px$. In the case of a nonzero p, E , one has the constraint of $x'/t' = v$. We suggest that in the rest frame there is also the localization of m_0 (linked to 3 co-ordinate axes, not the one of momentum.)

If one tries to create an equation linking (pc, E) and $(0, m_0 c c)$, one needs to introduce matrices (Dirac matrices). These anticommute (i.e. do not commute) and are linked with x, y, z, t , but do not explicitly act on x, y, z, t . The fact that they are linked to space-time and do not commute suggests (we argue) that one has non-isotropy in space-time and we associate this with the localization of rest mass. We note that the mathematics of this non-localization is very similar to that of physical angular momentum. For a photon, one has no rest mass and so no rest mass localization at a point and spin 1 for a circularly polarized photon is physical angular momentum.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gamma_matrices